

Nanda Devi Glacier Burst: A Study of Impact of Climate Change

Shtakshi Sharma¹, Sahab Deen²

¹M.Sc. (Geography) Scholar, Department of Geography, School of Humanities, Lovely Professional University, Phagwara, Punjab

²Assistant Professor, Department of Geography, School of Humanities, Lovely Professional University, Phagwara, Punjab

ABSTRACT

The Himalayan mountain range is the home of thousands of glaciers and approximately 19 to 20 rivers originated from these glaciers. The Himalayan mountain range is the youngest mountain range, venerable and fragile in nature. Several disasters took place in this region because of its sensitivity. Nanda Devi group of glaciers is home to 7 glaciers found in the Garhwal Himalayan belt. Bartoli, Kururntoli, Nanda Devi North, Nanda Devi South, Nandakna, Ramani, and Trishul are the parts of the Nanda Devi Group of Glaciers which lay in Chamoli district of Uttarakhand. On 7, February 2021 a flood occurred in Rontigad, Rishiganga and Dhauliganga, and Alakananda rivers due to Nanda Devi Glacier Burst. A general term used for glacial burst is Glacial Lake Outburst Flooding which is generated in this region due to the impact of climate change. Several hypothetical reasons are given by so many experts for this flood disaster like climate change, Glacial Lake Outburst Flooding (GLOF), warm winter, and rockslide with ice or avalanche. This alpine glacier disaster adversely impacts the lives of hundreds of people and two hydro projects worth 1,500 crores also destroyed in this flood disaster, even the settlement beside the river banks also adversely affected. This whole flood incident was an impact of climate change because the whole process is related to glacier retreating, melting, and glacial burst.

Keywords: Climate Change, Flood Disaster, Glacial Lake Outburst Flooding (GLOF), GlacierBurst, Retreating Glacier, Uttarakhand.

INTRODUCTION

Glaciers are the huge mass of ice that moves like a very slow river because of their own weight and gravity that's why these are also known as ice rivers. They are huge masses of ice that are formed due to consecutively snowfall in the same region or place year by year. Glaciers are formed in the region where the melting rate of ice is less than the rate of piles up of ice. When the fluffy snow crystals are converted into dense and tight ice pallets because of compression by continuous piles up of ice and less melting, the formation of glaciers happened. Glaciers took thousands or hundreds of years for their formation. There are two main types of glaciers: Alpine glaciers which are found in the Polar and temperate regions, as well as, found in tropical regions where the mountains are very high. The second one is Continent glaciers (Ice Sheets) are found in the Polar region for example Antarctica and the island of Greenland. Australia has no Glacier. Continental glaciers are found on a flat surface they are moving the center points in all directions and on the other hand, alpine glaciers move toward the valley.

Recently, Glacial Lake Outburst Flooding (GLOF) situation happened in the Garhwal Himalayan region of Uttarakhand. The Himalayan Mountain range is home to thousands of glaciers. On 7thFebruary2021, a highly devastating flood occurred in the Tapovan area of the Joshimath region in the Chamoli district of Uttarakhand. This region is found in the Garhwal division of Uttarakhand and highly ecological fragile and vulnerable region of Uttarakhand. India's second-highest mountain is Nanda Devi which is located in the Eastern Chamoli district of Uttarakhand. Nanda Devi Group of glaciers also located nearer to Nanda Devi Mountain. The northern division of this district made of high-grade metamorphic and igneous rocks and the southern division has consisted low grade metamorphic and sedimentary rocks. The Northern Division of Chamoli has high elevation mountains while the southern division has low elevation mountains. On 7thFebruary 2021 a massive flood disaster occurred in Uttarakhand's Chamoli district because of glacial lake burst or avalanche, which generated a flood in Rontigad which is a tributary of the Rishi Ganga River. Rishiganga is originated from Nanda Devi Glacier and Dhaul Ganga river, which is originated from Bashundhara Glacier. This situation increased the volume of the water of the Dhaul Ganga river which is tributary of Alaknanda and confluence with each other at Bishnu Prayag and also increased the velocity of the water. The massive chunks of ice, boulders, and sediments were flowed with the water and

cause a devastating incident in the Chamoli district. NTPC's Tapovan Vishnugad and Rishiganga Hydroelectric projects were completely washed away in this catastrophic flood. Several houses, which were situated on the bank of the river were destroyed by this flood, and hundreds of laborers of hydropower projects and people were also killed by this devastating flood. Alaknanda's water level also increased because Dhauliganga is its tributary. The reason for this catastrophic flood is unscientific construction works of development projects.

This research paper is an attempt to find out why and how the Nanda Devi glacier burst was the consequence of climate change? And how climate change will lead to glacier burst situation in the area in coming future. Thus, major objectives of the study are: a) to understand how and why the Nanda Devi Glacier burst was the result of climate change; and b) try to identify and reveal the glacier burst disaster occurrence in the area in coming future.

Study Area

Nanda Devi Glacier is located in the Tapovan area of the Chamoli district of Uttarakhand state in India. It is a part of the Garhwal division of Uttarakhand which is located under the Garhwal Himalayan belt in India. Coordinates of Nanda Devi Glacier are 30.41255591° N and 79.982853° E. Nanda Devi mountain which is the second-highest peak of India after Kanchenjunga is located at Chamoli district of Uttarakhand which means that elevation of this is approximately 800 to 8000 meters above sea level. The Nanda Devi Glacier arises from the mountain peak and divided into two parts North Nanda Devi and South Nanda Devi.

Source: Wikipedia, 2021, Nanda Devi Sanctuary sketch map.

The length of both the division is 19 KM. Nanda Devi glacier located between two valleys Rishiganga in the west and Goriganga valley in the East. The North division of the Chamoli district has consisted of high grade of metamorphic and igneous and the southern division has consisted of low grade sedimentary and metamorphic rocks. High mountain peaks are found in the Northern Chamoli district and low elevation mountain peaks are found in the Southern division. This means the Southern division of the Chamoli district is more fragile than the Northern division. Rishiganga originated from Nanda Devi Glacier and the confluence with Dhauliganga near Raini village and Dhauliganga is tributary of Alaknanda is originated from Bashundhara Glacier which is very nearer to Nanda Devi Glacier. Many pilgrimage sites like Badrinath, Hemkund Sahib, and tourist places like Valley of Flower are found in the Chamoli district of Uttarakhand. Two hydroelectric power projects of NTPC's Tapovan Vishnugad and Rishiganga Hydroelectric projects were settled in this district before the flood of 7th February 2021 which is generated due to glacial lake burst or avalanche Rontigad in Rontigad, Rishiganga, and Dhauliganga further tributary of Alaknanda.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present article is an qualitative academic exercise based on secondary data sources extracted from different study, reports and research and have been used to examine the Causes of Nanda Devi Glacier Burst in the study area in order to fulfill the objectives of the study.

Climate Change & Glacial Lake Outburst Flooding (GLOF)

IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) stated in 2001 that from the last hundred years, due to industrialization and greenhouse gases the mean temperature increased from 0.3 to 0.6 °C and it is likely that with the increase in Carbon emission mean temperature of the world will rise from 1.4°C to 5.8 °C in the next hundred years. IPCC expected that the mean temperature of the Indian subcontinent will also increase between 3.5 °C to 5.8 °C till 2100. Climate Change is one of the biggest reasons for glacial retreating and nowadays Glacial retreating and melting are the true indicators of climate change. Because of climate change, the process of glacial retreating of glaciers of China, Bhutan, India, and Nepal is increasing continuously. With the continuous process of glacial retreating the number and size of glacial lakes are increasing and it will lead the increased situations of GLOFs. These GLOF situations adversely affect the property and life of the people of the mountainous regions (Bajracharya et al.,2006).

Chamoli district of Uttarakhand is part of the Western Himalayan region which is very rich in biodiversity and also geologically this region is prone to disaster and very fragile in nature. Due to Climate change and increased human activities, the forest of the Western Himalayan region is under very risky conditions. Several birds, animals, and vegetation species are found in these forests. 315 bird species are found in this region. The process of glacial retreating is increased continuously because of climate change. Since 1981 the 0.18°C of the world's land and ocean temperature is increasing by every decade (Chowdhury & Rosencrang,2021).

According to Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in 2005 the global atmospheric concentration of CO₂ has increased from a pre-industrial value of about 280 PPM to 379 PPM. As determined from the ice cores this is the highest level of atmospheric concentration of CO₂ recorded in 2005 which is exceeded far by the natural range (180 to 300ppm) over the last 650,000 years. Although growth rates vary from year to year, the annual CO₂ concentration rate was greater during the last 10 years than it has been since the beginning of the continuous atmospheric measurement. According to the projections which indicate that the atmospheric CO₂ concentration will double from their pre-industrial values within the next 50 to 100 years. The outgoing radiations are not able to go out from the atmosphere and coming back to the surface because of the greenhouse gases which caused warming. The main reason for current global climate change is the increased concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere which is the most significant factor which affects global climate change (Bajracharya et al.,2007).

Several of the glacier-induced disasters are occurred in the Alpine Glacier region due to climate change means a change in the pattern of temperature and precipitation and some are triggered by external forces ice-capped volcanos, earthquakes, and anthropogenic activities. Non-climatic factors (topography, gradient, characteristics of glaciers) are also responsible for glacier change and glacier induced disasters. Glacial meltwater induced flood, Glacial lake outburst floods, glacial related debris flow, ice avalanches, Ice mass loss, paraglacial destabilization, and glacial surge are the disaster which is induced due to glacier change because of some climatic and non-climatic factors. Heat and flow of water are responsible for the disaster of the alpine glacier. At the present, the process of glacial retreating and melting water increased because of climate change and which leads to several glacial-born disasters (Wang et al.,2021).

Source: BBC News, Uttarakhand dam disaster, 8 February 2021.

Glacial activity is the main cause of the formation of glacial lakes. Glacier fluctuations are induced by many factors one of the factors is changing climatic conditions. Altitude and aspect precipitation, temperature, and the extent of debris cover are the controlling factors. The glacier inventory has many areas in the Himalaya and Nanda Devi is one of the areas which have been comparatively well investigated in terms of its glacier inventory. Many authors have attempted to correlate glacial stages in the Himalayas but the lack of detailed historical records on a regional Himalayan scale hinders the development of a chronology of glacial fluctuation (Vuichard & Zimmermann, 1987).

Due to the higher altitude in mountainous areas the water which was melted from glacier and lake water comes in direct contact with clouds. Due to the cold water of the lakes, the saturation vapors' pressure over the water remains very high because the temperature of the glacier lakes is below the freezing temperature. The sublimation process happened very often from the moraine-free glaciers or the freeze lakes in snout areas because of that the volume and depth of the cloud could be increased within a short time because the evaporated water immediately condenses over the snow droplets of the cloud. The micaceous sediments are very high in the Himalayan region because of that there are plenty numbers of freezing nuclei present in the atmosphere due to the excessive weathering and erosion processes of these micaceous elements. The small water droplets are converted into ice crystals because of these freezing nuclei and because of that, the cloud became heavier and denser. These heavy clouds move downwards and because of this they became unstable due to adiabatic heating and they can be collapsed within a small portion of areas. The rate of destruction became worst when this type of cloud is trapped inside a valley (Das, 2015).

Causes for Chamoli Disaster 2021

GLOFs Generated Flood in Downstream

Many glaciologists called the 7th February 2021 flood of Chamoli district of Uttarakhand was triggered by the glacial lake burst in the downstream river. Several proglacial lakes are found in the Himalayan region because of glacial retreating. These lakes bounded by big boulders and sediments and formed at the tips of the glaciers. GLOF event depends on the size or location of the glacial lake which burst. According to glaciologist Argha Banerjee, maybe there was such kind of Proglacial Lake was present in the region which was known to scientist because of this region of full of this kind of lakes.

Two days before this flood event an avalanche was triggered in this region. According to professor A P Dimiri who belongs to the school of environmental science from JNU that at this time of the year there is no possibility of any other factor which provide massive water to the situation, so most probably there was a proglacial lake present in the region (The Indian Express, Amitabh Sinha,2021).

Climate Change

UN Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change stated in their latest report that the number and size of proglacial lakes increased in mountain regions because of the high speed of glacial retreating and also the instability of mountain slopes increased due to the thawing process in the cryosphere of mountainous region. Assistant professor of IIT Indore Farooq Azam who belongs to the department of glaciology and hydrology stated that there was no such kind of lake present in the region according to satellite imagery and Google Earth images. He stated that maybe this flood havoc triggered by any pocket lake which was present under the glacier. Even the patterns of precipitation are also increased or decreased due to climate change (The Hindu, Jacob Koshy,2021).

Warm Winters

The warm winter is the main impact of climate change according to experts the range of ice is increased which is -2°C but after it were -6 to -20°C ; this range of ice leads to high melting in winter season also (The Hindu, Jacob Koshy,2021). After six decades the Uttarakhand recorded the warmest January in 2021 (Wang et al.,2021) which causes a high speed of glacial retreating.

Rockslide from Ronti Peak

Some researchers stated that the flood is generated due to the rockslide of one portion of Ronti Mountain. This rockslide triggered a flood in the downstream rivers because the ice and debris of the rockslide increase the intensity and velocity of the water. This whole process of rockslide with ice increased the flow downstream and led to the situation of flood in main streams (Shrestha et al.,2021)

Consequences

On the 7thFebruary 2021, massive flood havoc occurred in the Chamoli district of Uttarakhand. Hundreds of people died in this deluge. Approximately 70 people died in this disaster and 150 people remained missing (Khandekar,2021).

Source: Glacier Bursts in India, Leaving More Than 100 Missing in Floods. The New York Times. 7 February 2021.

Moreover, two hydroelectrical power projects of NTPC's were completely destroyed in this disaster. These projects were the Tapovan Vishnugad project and Rishiganga hydel project. Approximately there were losses of 1,500 crore Rupees

happened due to the devastation caused by flood in these projects (Khandekar, 2021). Besides, the settlements also adversely affected by flood those were settled beside the river banks in the study area.

DISCUSSION

When a glacier moves it eroded its path and generates a Depression nearer to its snout. The edges of the depression are surrounded by the deposition of sediments and filled by the melted water, ice of glaciers. This depression which is surrounded by sediments on the snout of glaciers and filled by water and ice is known as Moraine dammed Glacier Lake. Sometimes the moraine of this lake breaks and the glacial lake completely released into the downstream river because of high water and ice pressure, which generate due to glacial retreat, extreme rainfall, sudden accumulation of sediments and ice in the glacial lake due to avalanches, earthquakes, etc. The specific term used for this situation is GLOF (Glacial Lake Outburst Flooding). According to many experts the main reason for this glacier burst, or avalanche is climate change. This kind of situation generally occurs in the rainy and summer season but on 7th February 2021 GLOF situation was the result of warm winters, which was the actual result of Climate change. Climate change is a phenomenon that is influenced by human processes like, deforestation, industrialization, emission of greenhouse gases, urbanization, etc. Climate Change will also lead to other catastrophic events in the future.

Climate Change is the biggest issue nowadays because it changes the pattern of temperature, precipitation even it negatively affects human health. As above mentioned, that according to IPCC the global temperature increased 0.3°C to 0.6°C from the last hundred years, and also it will be predicted by IPCC the world's global mean temperature also will be increased from 1.4 °C to 5.8°C till the next hundred years. This increment of temperature also affects the global pattern of precipitation. This will lead to the high process of glacial melting and retreating in continent glaciers as well as alpine glacier regions. Incontinent Glacier, the ice sheet will melt due to high temperature and changing pattern of precipitation and cause a rise of sea level which adversely affected the life of the coastal region and so many other havocs. In the alpine glacier region, climate change increased the process of glacial retreating and melting which lead to several disasters. Due to climate change even, seasonal patterns also effaced because mountainous regions faced sometimes more warm winters which affect the freezing point of the water. In alpine glacier due to increase in temperature the melting and retreating speed also increased and which generate several proglacial lakes, moraine-dammed glacial lake and these are the cause of the GLOFs situation which further generate flood in downstream rivers. Even glacial avalanches are also triggered by climate change sometimes. So as a result of increasing temperature we can say that this kind of event will take place in future. Climate Change also adversely impacted human health.

CONCLUSION

A glacier burst is a natural event but caused by many factors which include human involvement or we can say human interference with nature in a destructive manner. The natural factors that cause the glacier burst are sudden rainfall, landslide and avalanche, and high intensity of glacial retreating. Human interference that caused the glacier burst is mainly by the high concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere or by global warming and climate change which causes the high atmospheric temperature and change in global rainfall patterns. The flood disaster of Chamoli district on 7th February 2021 was the result of the impact of climate change because this disaster took place in the winter season. According to IPCC as above mentioned the global mean temperature increase year by year. Climate change leads to glacial melting and glacial retreat which causes disasters related to glaciers in alpine and continental glacial regions. The result of this disaster was worst because hundreds of people died and two hydroelectrical projects worth 1500 crore were also destroyed. The exact cause of the Nanda Devi glacier burst is still unknown or in the research phase but by the satellite views, we can assume that the cause of the Nanda Devi glacier burst is a landslide or glacier burst. We cannot exactly stop these kinds of disasters in the future, but by making the environment stable with afforestation and low level of CO₂ concentration we can reduce the possibility of these kinds of events. Also, the increase of the population in these types of region, increase the loss by this type of disasters.

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